

MUSIC AS A CONCEPT IN ARCHITECTURE THROUGH MUSICAL COLUMNS AND CYMATICS PATTERN DESIGNS IN HAMPI INTERIORS

RAMAJI PRANAV 20111ID0007 B.DES. ID
Department of interior design
Dr. YSR Architecture and fine arts university Kadapa.
Kadapa Andhra Pradesh, India
E-mail: pranavbala.rj@gmail.com

Abstract— This research paper is all about the hampi vijayanagara empire vitthala temple's interiors and architecture. It includes interior construction technology and their details of science behind the construction of the musical columns and the use of cymatics patterns of ceiling designs to investigate the relation between the cymatic patterns and the musical columns to know their interlinked connection between them to know their concept

Keywords- musical columns, monolithic stone, silica, cymatic patterns, density, tonoscope, chladni plate.

I. INTRODUCTION

Historical interiors are all about the interior architecture which have the historical influence in this present generations which was constructed during the times of olden history. These have a vast scope to know about their ancient civilization their life style and their olden construction technology and their architectural style. This research is mainly focused to know the technology behind the design of musical columns and their stone characteristics and also to know the cymatics pattern designs on ceilings.

This research is carried out in Sri Vijaya vitthala temple in hampi which is the most identical temple is also a world heritage site in India. This is located on the southern banks of the Tungabhadra River in Karnataka which was ruled by the king Devaraya II. This temple was existed between 1422–1462 (wikipedia, n.d.)

The temple consists of (164m X 94.5m) area. The main identical features of this temple is musical columns which produce music and sound wave patterns in mahamandapam / rangamandapam (also called as the great stage). This mahamandapam consists of 56 pillars each have 3.6m height. Out of 56 columns 40 columns are regularly arranged to form the aisle and remaining 16 columns form rectangular court. These columns are made up of granite stone when these are struck with the fingers they produce different musical notes. This temple also consists of cymatic patterns on the ceilings made up of stones. Cymatics is the visual form of sound.

The research is to give the details of science and construction process behind the construction and processing of musical columns and cymatic patterns this also includes the techniques and processes involved to make this stone audible.

Figure 1 Photograph of the mahamandapam taken from the east direction showing musical columns in the pillars and position of cymatic patterns

Figure 2 Photograph of (a) the musical pillars in the musical column and (b) one of the cymatic pattern present on the ceilings of the mahamandapam

II. EXPERIMENTATIONS AND METHODOLOGY

This present study will deal with the analysing of the structural properties to find the construction techniques using materials and to decode the sound waves of the musical columns to link up with the existing cymatic patterns to know the relation between them the details of these columns and their position are mentioned in the Table I and Fig 1 respectively

A. Dimensional measurements

Dimensional measurements were taken according to the First study on detailed acoustical analysis and non-destructive characterization of the 11 most popular pillars which are known to produce sounds of different Indian musical instruments is given by (kumar)

TABLE I. Details of the musical pillars examined in depth.

Pillar number as per Fig. 1	Musical instruments they are correlated to	Number of musical columns in the pillar	Total height range (mm)	Diameter range (mm)	Ultrasonic velocity range (m/s)	Frequency range of the sound produced (Hz)		Average time for delay of amplitude to 1/20 of the peak in autocorrelation function (ms)
						Lower	Higher	
2 (east side)	Saptaswara (seven notes)	8	960–1180	75.6–99.5	5300–5500	243–396	687–1000	226
2 (north side)	—	6+1 (Cut)	960–1140	89–104	5250–5430	296–372	738–967	130
3	Panchtala (five tones)	9	870–950	62.5–100.5	4600–5300	442–588	1046–1280	215
4	Jaltarang (water instrument)	7	880–920	90.0–130	5400–5500	495–780	—	266
5	Mridanga (percussion instrument)	5	910–985	98–106.5	5300–5500	444–457	1148	178 (114–284)
11	Ghanta (bell)	6	910–985	102.7–111.2	5400–5740	533–656	953	500
14	Ghatam (earthen pot, percussion instrument)	12	1220–1250	102.7–122.5	5300–5600	305–454	774	300
16	Veena (sting instrument)	4	830–980	100.3–106.6	5200–5500	745–821	—	250
24	Tabla (percussion instrument)	10	1115–1120	97.3–107.0	5200–5600	296–407	—	188
3A	Damaru (small percussion instrument)	9	1170–1220	97.1–106.6	5200–5700	273–375	739–786	258
5A	Kerala Mridangam (percussion instrument)	5	1080–1130	115–122	5500–5600	338–412	783–901	295
20A	Shankha (shell)	5	940–1065	95.5–1127.5	5200–5450	399–471	983–1060	332
15A	Damaged				4200	680–760		91

The columns are visually noticed according to the data the columns were found to have larger dimensions at the bottommost portion and decreased it decreased almost continuously to the minimum at the uppermost portion. The diameter of the columns was measured at the lowest (maximum) and uppermost portions (minimum) by measuring the circumference with 0.5 mm accuracy. The shape of the columns were also noted.

B. Geological analysis of hampi

The middle portion of Karnataka with huge boulders have the composition of granite stone, relatively the stable geologic terrain was formed between 3.6 billion and 2.5 billion years ago. The monolithic block split due to varied natural forces it makes cracks eventually metamorphosed to form the balancing form of rocks. The rock belt of the area is now called the Eastern Dharwar Craton owing to their characters in lithologies and ages is dominantly granitic. EDC rocks, predominant around Hampi are called as younger granites, a supracrustal belts of sedimentary rocks in origin. The hampi ores also contains silica substance in the

rocks due to the chemically precipitated sediments of volcanic plutonic rocks which tends to show the various degrees of metamorphism recorded.

C. In situ metallography

In situ metallographic studies were carried out by first studies on nondestructive characterization of musical columns by Kumar et al [2] for identification of the type of material was performed to study the presence of micro cracks/pores in the column. It was carried out at two locations, i.e., the broken portions of two of the musical columns, one each in column 2 and 19. An in situ grinding machine was used. It polished the broken surface of the musical columns under continuous flow of water. A replica of the polished surface was taken using a replica tape to identify the features under an visual optical microscope.

D. Tonoscope/chladni plate resonance testing

This technique involves a chladni plate shown in fig 4, a resonance plate works when it vibrates. The sand particles present

Figure 3 plan of the mahamandapam indicating existing and damaged pillars and the musical columns in them

on the plate forms into different visual forms. The tonoscope is a software of a chladni plate it takes the audio signals digitally to the computer and makes the process resulting to produce cymatic wave forms as shown in fig 4 (d).

Figure 4 Image of (a) shows the chladni plate of classical technology (b) shows the modern chladni plate device and (c) shows the cymatic patterns formed by the sand on the plate due to sounds and (d) shows the modern tonoscope application of the chladni plate.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Detailed plan of the mahamandapam

Plan of great stage shows the plan of mahamandapam in vitthala temple it shows the position of pillars and musical columns in them. The great stage consists of 56 main pillars and out of them 41 columns are present and the remaining pillars are damaged. Out of 54 pillars 15 pillars (1, 1a, 3, 3a, 5, 5a, 8, 8a, 11, 17a, 15, 19a, 23, 23a, and 24) are damaged accordingly and the rectangular court ceiling is completely fallen of.

B. In situ metallography

Figure 5 shows typical microstructures observed on the broken columns, by Kumar (Non-destructive characterization of musical pillars of Mahamandapam of Vitthala Temple) respectively. The microstructures are found to be similar to that of a typical granite stone. It also proves that the columns are not hollow.

Figure 5 Typical as polished microstructure in cut surface of the musical columns : (a) pillar 2 and (b) pillar 19

C. Dimensional measurements

Table I provides the data of musical columns it shows the range of length and the average diameter of each musical column of the pillars. It is clear that the columns contains larger dimensions at the bottommost regions and it decreases continuously to the minimum at the upperpart of the columns according to the table I we can notice that columns are found to be about 10% across about 1m length of the column from the bottom to the upper part. The shapes of the columns are considered to be noticed in different shapes such as cylinder, rectangular, octagonal, and square shapes.

D. Construction process of musical columns

The construction of the musical columns involve many steps detailed construction technique is mentioned below.

Step 1: segregation of rocks

In this stage sculptors of hampi segregate the rocks from the mountains according to geological analysis, hampi consists of monolithic igneous rocks. They have collected the rocks and made it into their required blocks

Step II: Changing the intrinsic density of the blocks by adding silica

According to the geological analysis it concludes that there are metallic ores consisting of large amount of silica. So they used the silica to mix it with the igneous stone to change the density by rock melting technique.

Intrinsic Density of the column is = mass / volume

Mass: Mass is defined as the amount of matter present in an object.

Volume: volume is the amount of space occupied by any three-dimensional solid

This statement concludes that the density of the rock can be changed by changing its:

- Its mass and volume.
- Its shape and size of the column.
- Its length and width of the column.
- Its Dimensional factors

Step II: Rock melting technique

In this technique the granite rock blocks and silica materials are brought to the giant furnace. The giant furnace is heated up to 2500⁰c temperature. The rock is melted in the furnace and the required proportions of silica such as 1:2 1:3, 1:4, 2:1, 2:3, 3:1, 3:4, 4:1 are added to the rock to change its density. The melted molten rock lava substance is remolded to the desired shapes. The remolded slabs are again then carved into required shapes such as circular, rectangular, square, hexagonal and octagonal shapes etc.

Step IV: Additional factors influenced musical columns.

Musical columns in hampi are molded as a bar of circular cross-section it undergoes flexural vibrations. The pillars with the musical columns of monolithic structure bar is considered to be clamped at both the ends as shown in fig 8. The vibrations are transverse in nature there is no tension in the bar and the restoring force is mainly due to elastic forces within the bar thus makes the bar to produce high frequency sound waves.

Figure 6 shows the forces and no tension in the bar and the restoring force is mainly due to elastic forces within the bar

E. Decoding cymatic patterns and their construction

These cymatic sounds are generated using chladni plate as shown in fig 4 (a,b,c & d) but the ancient style of making cymatics include resonating plates, they used different sounds to resonate the plate thus the sand upon it forms into different visual patterns.

F. Chladni plate resonance testing.

In this process we can see the results of the different cymatic patterns of different sounds such as ghanta, mridanga, shanka and veena sounds recorded digitally by means of tonoscope software. The readings of the sounds are given below

Cymatic pattern 1

Cymatic pattern 2

cymatic pattern 3

cymatic pattern 4

Figure 7 Patterns of cymatics in tonoscope software which was collected by sending input of musical columns of vijaya vitthala temple hampi

Hampi cymatic patterns 1

Hampi cymatic patterns 2

Hampi cymatic pattern 3

Figure 8 Photographs of existing cymatic patterns on hampi which are similar to the computer generated tonoscope patterns

The cymatic patterns of hampi have similarities to that of modern day digital cymatic patterns, these patterns have the co-relation and connection between the cymatic patterns present on the ceilings of hampi and the sounds produced by the musical columns, the sounds of the columns are matching with the existing cymatic patterns as shown in the figures. These patterns might be recorded according to their music by using resonating plate technique.

These patterns are influenced from the cultures of hampi kingdom as it is mentioned in the history that king devaraya II and his wife loved music and dance so they encouraged the artists and architects to show up their musical art form on their construction for the next generations to show up their construction technology.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study reports the interior construction technology used by hampi artists and techniques of which they have used to construct the musical columns, and this also contains the investigation of the hampi cymatic patterns to match with the modern day cymatic patterns using Digital computerised software's. This research also contains the correlation between the musical columns and the cymatic patterns. By this research we can conclude that there is a vast scope in our interiors from the history to the present through various technologies, techniques and various innovative concepts.

This will be an inspiration for the present modern day interiors and applications.

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LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1 Photograph of the mahamandapam taken from the east direction showing musical columns in the pillars and position of cymatic patterns 1
- Figure 2 Photograph of (a) the musical pillars in the musical column and (b) one of the cymatic pattern present on the ceilings of the mahamandapam 1
- Figure 3 plan of the mahamandapam indicating existing and damaged pillars and the musical columns in them 3
- Figure 4 Image of (a) shows the chladni plate of classical technology (b) shows the modern chladni plate device and (c) shows the cymatic patterns formed by the sand on the plate due to sounds and (d) shows the modern tonoscope application of the chladni plate. 3
- Figure 5 Typical as polished microstructure in cut surface of the musical columns : (a) pillar 2 and (b) pillar 19 3
- Figure 6 shows the forces and no tension in the bar and the restoring force is mainly due to elastic forces within the bar 4
- Figure 7 Patterns of cymatics in tonoscope software which was collected by sending input of musical columns of vijaya vitthala temple hampi 5
- Figure 8 Photographs of existing cymatic patterns on hampi which are similar to the computer generated tonoscope patterns 5